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Seroprevalence of Toxoplasmosis: Comparative study between Migrant Workers from the Indian Subcontinent and local Malaysian workers

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ABSTRACT

Background: Primary toxoplasmosis is usually subclinical, but in severely immunocompromised patients it may be life-threatening. For this reason, it could be important to monitor situations related to non-noticeable diseases among foreign arrivals in a country. In this study, we aimed to survey toxoplasmosis among migrants from Indian subcontinent to Malaysia.

Methods: In a prospective, observational study, a serological evaluation on toxoplasmosis among 91 migrants from Indian Subcontinent in Malaysia was conducted in a plantation and a detention camp. We used study subject information sheet for demographic information and venous blood samples for serological study to determine *Toxoplasma gondii* IgG and IgM antibodies. The control group was composed of 198 local Malaysians working in the same plantation and detention camp.

Results: The age of study participants ranged from 19-45 years (geometric mean 29.9).

Except for the Nepalese, none of these migrants from the Indian Subcontinent were positive for IgM. IgG positive rates among the Nepalese, Indians and Pakistani were 46.2%, 6.6% and 5.9% respectively. All workers from Sri Lanka had 0.0% prevalence rate for both IgG and IgM. The prevalence rates of 44.9% was significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher among local Malaysian workers when compared to migrant workers (18.8%). No significant difference in the prevalence rates was noted among the migrants or local workers when they were grouped according to agricultural and non-agricultural occupations.

Conclusion: Our data demonstrate that, with the exception of Nepalese population, there is a low frequency of toxoplasmosis infection among migrants from Indian subcontinent to Malaysia. A routine screening for toxoplasmosis may be indicated for sub-groups of migrants in this country.

Key words: Toxoplasmosis, Migrants, Indian Subcontinent, Malaysia

INTRODUCTION

Toxoplasma gondii is a protozoan parasite that is endemic worldwide and is a major opportunistic pathogen in immunocompromised hosts. Infection is mainly acquired by ingestion of food, water or soil that is contaminated with oocysts shed by cats, or by eating undercooked or raw meat containing tissue cysts [1]. Primary infection is usually subclinical, but in severely immunocompromised patients it may be life-threatening. Most primary infections subsequently phase into chronic infections in which the parasite persists in tissue cysts, mainly in the brain, retina, skeletal and cardiac muscles [2]. These chronic infections probably persist indefinitely throughout life and may remain undiagnosed until or unless it is reactivated as a result of severe immune suppression [3]. For the diagnosis of *T. gondii* infection, detection of the organism itself is confirmative but very difficult. Thus, most clinical laboratories use serological tests to detect antibodies against *T. gondii* such as the latex agglutination (LA) test, ELISA (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay) and indirect fluorescent antibody test because of its high specificity and sensitivity [4].

Seroprevalence in different populations may vary according to different environments, social customs and habits, especially dietary habits [5, 6]. Analysis of worldwide reports indicated, on the average about 38.5% humans, 32.9% cats and 24.2% goats were seropositive for toxoplasmosis [7, 8, 9]. Due to globalization phenomenon and international travel for labor, pleasure and refugee, these activities have the potential to spread diseases. The arrival of migrant workers in Malaysia since the

1980s has raised the concern that some formerly unknown diseases may be inadvertently brought into the country [10, 11]. Although most of the identified infections were also endemic in the country, the continuous introduction of these infections may, in the long term, influence the epidemiology and further compromise the efforts in control and prevention. The aim of this study was to estimate the prevalence of toxoplasmosis among migrants from Indian subcontinent to Malaysia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Type of study and sampling: The type of the study was prospective, observational. All subjects who gave their consents were involved in this study.

Study site and subjects: An isolated oil palm plantation within a rural setting and a detention camp located at the fringes of rubber plantations and orchards were selected as the sites for undertaking the present study. The survey involved 501 migrant workers from different Asian countries. Among these workers there were 91 workers from Indian Subcontinent (45 Indians, 26 Nepali, 17 Pakistani and 3 from Sri Lanka). For comparison, the study included 198 local Malaysian workers who are living and working in the plantation where the survey was conducted and Malaysian police and immigration personnel serving in the detention camp.

Data collection and analysis: Laboratory assessment was conducted on sera from single collection of blood samples. After separation, the serum was heat-inactivated at 56⁰ C for 30 minutes, and followed clarification by centrifugation. The samples were initially screened for *Toxoplasma* IgG

antibody by the immunofluorescent antibody test (IFAT). The significant titer was defined as 1:64 and above. Positive samples were further titrated at two-fold dilutions to determine the end-point values. All serum samples were also tested for IgM antibody by captured enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The samples were diluted to 1:100. The absorbance of the wells was read within 15 minutes from the end of the assay at 450 nm against the reference wavelength at 620 nm. Demographic information was gathered by using study subject information sheet. Verbal consent was taken from all subjects participated in this study.

Statistical analyses were conducted by using SPSS version 10.0 for Windows 2004. Chi-square test for significance at 95% confidence level and p value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The overall distribution of *Toxoplasma* IgG and IgM antibodies among the migrants who came from different Asian countries (Indian subcontinent, Indonesia, Bangladesh, Thailand and China) was compared to that of the local residents. IgG prevalence among local residents was significantly ($p= 0.009$)

higher than the migrant workers (Table I). All subjects involved in this study were male workers of an age range between 19-45 years.

Two hundred and one workers had been issued the permits by the relevant government authorities to work in the plantation. Besides the legal migrant workers, the study involved 300 foreigners who had entered the country without legal papers.

In this article we will present only the results of study subjects from Indian subcontinent. Results for other migrants' sub-groups were presented in other articles. Analysis of IgG positive rate of the Nepalese migrants against that of other detainees from India and Pakistan showed that the Nepalese had a significantly higher antibody positive rate of $p= 0.0001$, $p= 0.01$ respectively. However the prevalence rate among local workers is still significantly higher ($p<0.001$) when compared to the total prevalence rate among workers from Indian subcontinent (Table II). Table III shows the IgG titres of the studied subjects tested positive for toxoplasmosis. Statistical analysis didn't established significant difference in the infection rates between those who worked in the field and those who engaged in non-agricultural activities (Table IV).

Table I: Overall distribution of *Toxoplasma* IgG and IgM antibodies among the migrant and local subjects in the host country.

Study subjects	Total number of samples	IgG-positive	IgM-positive
		Number (%)	Number (%)
Migrants	501	171 (34.1%)	26 (5.2%)
Locals	198	89 (44.9%)	17 (8.6%)
P value		0.009	0.17
95% CI		-0.189 to -0.031	-0.069 to 0.009

Table 2: Distribution of *Toxoplasma* IgG and IgM antibodies according to countries of origin of the study subjects

Countries of Origin	Total number of samples	IgG-positive Number (%)	IgM-positive Number (%)
Nepal	26	12 (46.2%)	3 (11.5%)
India	45	3 (6.6%)	0 (0.0%)
Pakistan	17	1 (5.9%)	0 (0.0%)
Sri Lanka	3	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)
Total	91	16 (18.8%)	3 (3.5%)
Local workers	198	89 (44.9%)	17 (8.6%)
P value		< 0.001	0.17
95% CI		-0.380 to -0.140	-0.111 to 0.011

Table 3: *Toxoplasma* IgG antibody titres of study subjects

Countries of Origin	Total positive samples	Median	Mode (Number of samples)	Range
<i>Nepal</i>	12	768	2048 (4)	128-2048
<i>India</i>	3	256	<i>Not applicable</i>	64-1024
<i>Pakistan</i>	1	<i>N.A</i>	<i>Not applicable</i>	64
<i>Overall</i>	16	256	64 (40)	64-4048
<i>Local workers</i>	89	256	64 (27)	64-4096

Table 4: Samples tested positive for toxoplasmosis IgG antibodies in relation to occupations of the migrants and local workers study subjects

	Agriculture	Non-agriculture	P value
<i>Legal migrants</i>	41 (29.1%)	13 (21.7%)	0.31
<i>Illegal migrants</i>	55 (46.2%)	62 (34.3%)	0.06
<i>Local workers</i>	31 (55.4%)	58(44.6%)	0.80
<i>Total</i>	127 (18.2%)	133 (19.0%)	0.96

DISCUSSION

In East and Southeast Asia seroprevalence rate of *T. gondii* infection is generally lower than that reported from Europe and Americas [12, 13]. In Europe, the human seroprevalence varies from country to another but it can reach 10% to 50% [14]. In America there is important variation between geographical regions. At the Atlantic coast the prevalence can reach up to 63% [15]. However, the results of the present study indicated that toxoplasmosis was a common finding among migrants to this country.

Among the different groups of positive cases identified in the present study, the highest seroprevalence rate of 46.2% was found among Nepalese workers. *Toxoplasma* infection in Nepal was widely distributed irrespective of vast diversity in geography and ethnicity [16, 17]. The major contributing factor to such high prevalence was attributed to the habitual ingestion of minced raw meat or insufficiently cooked meat by some ethnic groups.

The emergence of *T. gondii* infection as an important opportunistic infection in 67.8% of the HIV/AIDS patients in Bombay was reported [18]. In the general Indian population, about 30.9% of immunocompetent adults were positive for the infection [19]. The present study identified 6.6% of the illegal migrants from India being positive for *Toxoplasma* IgG.

The negative findings among workers from Sri Lanka, may be due to religious causes since they are Budi (don't eat meat) or may be due to the little number of studied subjects (only 3).

From the results of the present study, the overall seroprevalence rate of

toxoplasmosis IgG in the Malaysian local subjects were 44.9%. As it is not a common practice among the locals to consume raw or undercooked meat, it is more likely that the infection was acquired through the ingestion of mature *T. gondii* oocysts shed by the infected

reservoirs. Although there were several reports on the seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis in the local population, it should be cautioned that the locals in the camp as well as those in the plantation were selected groups of study subjects in specific study sites. The majority of the local subjects of the present study were born and bred in the same plantation isolated from the outside. The continuous transmission and re-exposures to the infection in the 'closed' environment may have contributed to the higher prevalence rate noted in our study. The prevalence rates deduced from the present survey therefore may not be considered as representative of the general population.

The nature of occupations is known to pose a risk to infection by *Toxoplasma gondii*. To investigate any possible relationship between the acquisition of toxoplasmosis and occupations, the illegal migrants were grouped according to their occupational activities prior to arriving in the host country or before being detained in the detention camp. A majority of these migrants were involved in farming activities in their home countries, with the rest in non-agricultural activities. As the legal migrant workers had been in the plantation for about 3.5 years on the average, their occupations were defined according to the nature of work at the time when the survey was undertaken.

For the purpose of this investigation, occupations that involved agricultural activities included planting, harvesting, weeding and general maintenance of the plots. Non-agricultural occupations essentially included activities in processing and production in the oil palm mills, and other general jobs.

The results of the present study did not indicate any significant difference in the prevalence rates between those who were engaged in agricultural and non-agricultural occupations. This can be due to the fact that non-agricultural workers may not be directly involved in agricultural pursuits, but the confinement to the same environment where toxoplasmosis is being actively transmitted would have subjected them to the same risk factors. The author did not have the opportunity to study non-occupational risk factors. There was a time limitation to do a follow up study for dietary habits, behavioural risks, environmental conditions, socioeconomic strata and standards of hygiene. Future study of toxoplasmosis in any community should analyse in more details other important risk factors that influence the transmission of the disease.

CONCLUSION

The results showed that toxoplasmosis was not uncommon among the Asian migrant workers and local Malaysians. Statistical analysis did not established significant difference in the infection rates between those who worked in the field and those who engaged in non-agricultural activities ($p>0.05$). Our data demonstrate that, with the exception of Nepalese population, there is a low frequency of toxoplasmosis infection among migrants from Indian

subcontinent to Malaysia. A routine screening for toxoplasmosis may be indicated for sub-groups of migrants in this country.

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